

EFFECT OF VIDEO GAMES ON WORK AND STUDY ATTITUDES OF GRADE FOUR PUPILS IN THREE SCHOOLS OF VALENCIA CITY DISTRICT III

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Effect of Video Games on Work and Study Attitudes of Grade Four Pupils in Three Schools of Valencia City District III

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Abstract

The study aimed to assess the frequency and type of video games played by Grade Four pupils, the time spent gaming per week, teachers' perceptions of video games' effects on study attitudes, and gender differences in gaming habits. Conducted in three schools of Valencia City District III—Vintar Elementary School, Kahaponan Elementary School, and San Isidro Elementary School—the study employed a descriptive research design. A total of 109 pupils and five teachers participated, with data gathered through questionnaires. Statistical tools such as percentage, mean, standard deviation, rank, and t-test were used for analysis. Findings showed that fighting games were the most frequently played, though pupils spent limited time on gaming. Teachers agreed that video games influence pupils' work and study attitudes. While no significant gender difference was found in overall gaming frequency, role-playing games showed a notable gender-based variation. Recommendations for parents include monitoring the type of games children play, selecting age-appropriate and educational games, limiting screen time, and encouraging alternative activities for balanced development. Teachers should closely monitor attendance, use engaging teaching materials, and discourage pupils from visiting computer shops during school hours. Pupils are encouraged to prioritize studies, choose educational games, and follow parental guidance.

Keywords: *video games, effect, work and study attitudes*

Introduction

Playing video games has become a popular leisure activity for children today. It has become their preferred form of play and favorite pastime. According to VanDeventer and White (2002), many children now choose video games as their primary form of entertainment rather than engaging with peers or family members, often causing concern among parents and teachers. With the rapid advancement of technology, traditional games in society have transformed into digital games, with video games becoming the dominant form.

Video games first emerged in the early 1970s and are defined as electronically controlled games played on various platforms, including arcade machines, personal computers, and gaming consoles. In the present day, video games have become prevalent not only in urban areas but also in rural communities. Internet cafés, which offer services like web browsing, chatting, emailing, and gaming, are now common in both urban and rural areas. Many children engage in video gaming using consoles, computers, or arcade machines. Video games are easily accessible in homes, mini-grocery stores, and even sari-sari stores, with arcade machines being especially popular in rural locations.

The time and frequency children spend playing video games have risen significantly, often reaching addiction levels. Addiction, as defined by Egger and Rauterberg (1996), is an adverse condition characterized by a persistent inability to quit or control the use of a substance or engagement in a behavior. Video gaming can lead to addiction in children, where they feel compelled to continue playing even when they desire to stop. These games allow children to perform actions they cannot achieve in real life, providing a sense of accomplishment and satisfaction. Consequently, children may become daydreamers, unable to translate the determination they exhibit in games into real-life ambitions. Many children develop an obsession with video games; they skip classes to play, spend their allowances on games, and dedicate hours to gaming at the expense of homework, meals, and sleep.

Video games are frequently the subject of research due to their perceived influence on children's behavior. Studies often suggest that video games contribute to violent and aggressive tendencies in children. Gentile et al. (2004) state that video games have an addictive effect. On the other hand, several studies highlight the potential benefits of video gaming. Shaffer et al. (2005) argue that children can learn valuable skills from video games, comparing the activity to mental exercise. Video games can enhance problem-solving abilities, perseverance, pattern recognition, hypothesis testing, estimation skills, inductive reasoning, resource management, logistics, memory, quick thinking, and sound judgment.

Additionally, video games can improve hand-eye coordination, spatial awareness, imagination, geometric reasoning, mathematical thinking, and visualization of scientific concepts like physics or chemistry (Cesarone, 1994).

Video games, despite their benefits, often face criticism for their detrimental impact on children's behavior. Anderson and Bushman (2002) propose that violent games foster aggression by promoting hostile beliefs and attitudes, thereby shaping aggressive behavioral patterns and expectations. Bushman and Anderson (2002) found that exposure to violent games can “automatically prime aggressive thoughts.” Their research concluded that players with prior experience in violent games exhibit heightened aggression when confronted. Children with high levels of hostility are more likely to engage in physical altercations, with violent video games often blamed for such real-life actions.

Excessive video gaming can lead to problems such as strained social relationships with family and friends, poor academic or professional performance, and gaming addiction. Children often dedicate more time to gaming because of the pleasure and satisfaction it provides. However, this significant time investment can result in communication difficulties with family and peers, adversely affecting their academic and social lives (National Institute of Mental Health, 2005).

To establish a baseline for this study, the researcher conducted a preliminary survey among Grade Four pupils to determine whether they play video games. The results revealed that most pupils do. Teachers were also asked to rank factors influencing pupils' work and study habits. Out of five options, parents, video games, teachers, classmates, and environment ranked second.

Both parents and teachers are deeply concerned about the impact of video games on children. Many children spend more time gaming than studying, often going to computer shops to play their favorite video games. Given its widespread popularity, completely removing video games from children's lives may be challenging. Children's routines have ingrained video games, making their prohibition challenging. However, improper use of video games poses significant risks. Their effects range from promoting violent behavior to neglecting academic responsibilities. Therefore, addressing this issue is crucial to mitigating its adverse consequences.

These critical perspectives further motivated the researcher to explore the impact of video games on the work and study habits of Grade Four pupils in three schools within Valencia City District III.

Research Questions

The main problem of this study is to determine the effect of playing video games on work and study attitudes of Grade Four Pupils in three schools of Division of Valencia City District III. Specifically, it attempts to answer the following questions:

1. How often do Grade Four pupils play video games in terms of the following types:
 - 1.1. action;
 - 1.2. adventure;
 - 1.3. fighting;
 - 1.4. puzzle;
 - 1.5. role-playing;
 - 1.6. simulations;
 - 1.7. sports; and
 - 1.8. strategy games?
2. How much time do they spend on playing video games per week?
3. How do teachers perceive the effect of video games on work and study attitudes of Grade Four pupils?
4. Is there a significant difference in the frequency of playing video games when the respondents were grouped according to gender?

Methodology

Research Design

The study utilized the descriptive research method, which involved the systematic processes of data collection, processing, analysis, and interpretation. The results were presented in tables and discussions, highlighting the frequency of video game usage, the types of games played, the amount of time spent playing, and the impact of video games on the behavior and attitudes of schoolchildren. The researcher developed a questionnaire designed to gather data for statistical analysis, aiming to capture teachers' observations regarding the influence of video games on pupils' study habits and attitudes.

Respondents

The participants of the study were the Grade Four pupils and their advisers from three schools in Valencia City District III during the School Year 2011-2012.

The study employed purposive sampling, focusing specifically on Grade Four pupils who engage in video gaming and their respective advisers as the respondents. Table 1 presents the population and sample included in the research.

Table 1. *Population and Sample of Grade Four Pupils*

Name of School	Population of Grade 4 Pupils			Actual Pupils who played Video Games		
	M	F	T	M	F	T
Kahaponan E/S	41	22	63	28	16	44
San Isidro E/S	32	33	65	24	11	35
Vintar E/S	20	26	46	15	15	30
Total	93	81	174	67	42	109

Instrument

Survey questionnaires were utilized to collect relevant data for the study. The questions included in the survey were developed based

on a review of related literature and studies and were formulated by the researcher with guidance from the adviser.

The instrument consisted of two parts. Part I was designed for pupils and included questions about the frequency of playing various types of video games and the number of hours spent playing per week.

Part II was intended for Grade Four teachers and contained questions regarding their perceptions of the impact of video gaming on the work habits and study attitudes of Grade Four pupils.

Data Analysis

The data collected in this study were analyzed using descriptive statistics. Qualitative data were presented based on the responses provided by the participants, as outlined in the questionnaire. The analysis was guided by the conceptual framework.

For research questions 1 and 3, the mean and rank were utilized. For research question 2, frequency and percentage were applied. In addressing research question 4, a t-test was conducted to determine if there was a significant difference in the frequency of video game playing among the pupils based on gender.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the analysis and interpretation of the data collected. The discussion is organized according to the research questions of the study: the frequency of playing various types of video games, the amount of time spent playing video games per week, teachers' perceptions of the impact of video games on the work and study attitudes of Grade Four pupils, and the significant difference in the frequency of video game playing and its effect on work and study attitudes based on gender.

Problem 1. How often do Grade Four pupils play video games in terms of the following types: action, adventure, fighting, puzzle, role-playing, simulations, sports, and strategy games?

Selecting the appropriate type of video game is crucial. Table 2 presents the frequency of action and adventure game playing among Grade Four pupils from the three schools in Valencia City District III. The action games considered in this study include Halo, GTA San Andreas, Jedi Knight, Enter the Matrix, and Plants vs. Zombies, while the adventure games surveyed are Half-life, The Legend of Zelda, King's Quest, The Secret World, and Tomb Raider. The researcher included these examples of action and adventure games in the survey to determine which of them were most frequently played by Grade Four pupils.

Table 2. *The Frequency of Playing Action and Adventure Games*

<i>Action Games</i>		<i>Mean</i>	<i>Rank</i>	<i>Description</i>
1.	Plants vs. Zombies	2.82	1	Sometimes
2.	GTA San Andreas	2.56	2	Rarely
3.	Jedi Knight	1.97	3	Rarely
4.	Halo	1.96	4	Rarely
5.	Enter the Matrix	1.95	5	Rarely
6.	Over All Mean	2.25		Rarely
<i>Adventure Games</i>		<i>Mean</i>	<i>Rank</i>	<i>Description</i>
1.	Tomb Raider	2.19	1	Rarely
2.	The Secret World	2.02	2	Rarely
3.	King's Quest	1.99	3	Rarely
4.	The Legend Of Zelda	1.83	4	Rarely
5.	Half-Life	1.80	5	Never
	Over All Mean	1.96		Rarely

Note: The scale use in the table is never (1.00-1.80), rarely (1.81 – 2.60), sometimes (2.61 – 3.40), most of the time (3.41 – 4.20), and always (4.21 – 5.00)

As shown in Table 2, the action game Plants vs. Zombies received the highest mean response of 2.82, which corresponds to a rating of "sometimes" and ranked first among the action games. The second-ranked game, GTA San Andreas, received a mean response of 2.56, indicating that it was rated as "rarely" played. Jedi Knight ranked third with a mean response of 1.97, also rated as "rarely" played. Halo ranked fourth with a mean response of 1.96, also rated as "rarely" played, and Enter the Matrix ranked last with a mean response of 1.95, rated as "rarely" played as well.

Regarding the adventure games, all except Half-life were rated as "rarely" played, with mean responses ranging from 1.83 to 2.19. Tomb Raider, which ranked first, received a mean response of 2.19. The Secret World received 2.02, King's Quest had 1.99, and The Legend of Zelda ranked fourth with 1.83. However, Half-Life had the lowest mean response of 1.80, rated as "never" played.

The findings reveal that Grade Four pupils in the three schools in Valencia City District III exhibit minimal interest in adventure games, which is unexpected considering their educational value. Adventure games, recognized for promoting critical thinking, are beneficial for youngsters as they frequently entail problem-solving and education.

Research conducted by Daves & Dumbleton (2001), Pillay (2003), and Sandford & Williamson (2005) indicates that adventure games possess potential for instructional applications.

Table 3. *The Frequency of Playing Fighting and Puzzle Games*

<i>Fighting Games</i>		<i>Mean</i>	<i>Rank</i>	<i>Description</i>
1.	Mortal Kombat	4.54	1	Always
2.	Dota	5.11	2	Most of the Time
3.	Street Fighter	4.10	3	Most of the time
4.	Super Smash Bros.	3.99	4	Most of the time
5.	Dead or Alive	3.93	5	Most of the time
Over All Mean		4.13		Most Of The Time
<i>Puzzle Games</i>		<i>Mean</i>	<i>Rank</i>	<i>Description</i>
1.	Dragon Ball	3.17	1	Sometimes
2.	Solitaire	2.29	2.5	Rarely
3.	Bejeweled	2.29	2.5	Rarely
4.	Tetris	2.25	4	Rarely
5.	Frogger	2.12	5	Rarely
Over All Mean		2.42		Rarely

Note: The scale use in the table is never (1.00-1.80), rarely (1.81 – 2.60), sometimes (2.61 – 3.40), most of the time (3.41 – 4.20), and always (4.21 – 5.00)

The responses of Grade Four pupils in the three schools of Valencia City District III regarding their frequency of playing fighting and puzzle games are summarized in Table 3. The fighting games considered in this study include Dota, Mortal Kombat, Street Fighter, Super Smash Bros., and Dead or Alive, while the puzzle games are Tetris, Frogger, Bejeweled, Solitaire, and Dragon Ball.

Among the fighting games, Mortal Kombat was the most frequently played, with the highest mean response of 4.54, indicating that it was rated as "always" played. Dota followed closely with a mean response of 4.11, while Street Fighter came next with a mean response of 4.10, a very slight difference of 0.01. Super Smash Bros. had a mean response of 3.99, and Dead or Alive ranked last with a mean response of 3.93, both of which were rated as "most of the time" played.

In contrast, puzzle games were less frequently played compared to fighting games, as indicated by the lower mean responses across all puzzle games. Among the puzzle games, Dragon Ball had the highest mean response of 3.17, rated as "sometimes" played by the pupils. It was followed by Bejeweled and Solitaire, both tied with mean responses of 2.29, indicating they were "rarely" played. Tetris, a new game on Facebook, received a mean response of 2.25, and Frogger had the lowest mean of 2.12, with both games rated as "rarely" played.

In general, pupils predominantly engaged in fighting games, whereas puzzle games were infrequently played. This indicates that fighting games are the most favoured video games among Grade Four pupils in the three schools of Valencia City District III. Nonetheless, the content of fighting games is considered unsuitable for children due to their violent nature, rendering them unfit for young audiences.

Table 4. *The Frequency of Playing Role-Playing and Simulation Games*

<i>Role-Playing Games</i>		<i>Mean</i>	<i>Rank</i>	<i>Description</i>
1.	Final Fantasy	2.61	1	Sometimes
2.	Blue Dragon	2.44	2	Rarely
3.	Knights of the Old Republic	2.21	3	Rarely
4.	Zelda	2.14	4	Rarely
5.	Secret of Mana	2.03	5	Rarely
Over All Mean		2.29		Rarely
<i>Simulation Games</i>		<i>Mean</i>	<i>Rank</i>	<i>Description</i>
1.	Crime City	3.21	1	Sometimes
2.	Rollercoaster Tycoon	2.41	2	Rarely
3.	Sim City	2.23	3	Rarely
4.	Spore	2.19	4	Rarely
5.	Secret Weapons over Normandy	2.06	5	Rarely
Over All Mean		2.42		Rarely

Note: The scale use in the table is never (1.00-1.80), rarely (1.81 – 2.60), sometimes (2.61 – 3.40), most of the time (3.41 – 4.20), and always (4.21 – 5.00)

Regarding role-playing and simulation games, the results show that Final Fantasy is the most frequently played role-playing game among the pupils, with a mean response of 2.61, rated as "sometimes" played. It is followed by Blue Dragon, which has a mean response of 2.44, indicating it is "rarely" played. Next, Knights of the Old Republic received a mean response of 2.21 and is also rated as "rarely" played. Zelda ranks third with a mean response of 2.14, rated as "rarely," and Secret of Mana ranks last with a mean response of 2.03. These findings suggest that role-playing games are generally played "rarely," as indicated by the small mean responses, with an overall mean of 2.29.

For simulation games, the study included Sim City, Crime City, Rollercoaster Tycoon, Spore, and Secret Weapons Over Normandy. Among these, Crime City had the highest mean response of 3.21, indicating that it is "sometimes" played by the pupils. It is followed by Rollercoaster Tycoon, which has a mean response of 2.41, rated as "rarely" played. Sim City ranks third with a mean response of

2.23, also rated as "rarely" played. Spore follows with a mean response of 2.19 and is rated as "rarely" played. Lastly, Secret Weapons Over Normandy ranks fifth with a mean response of 2.06, also rated as "rarely" played.

In conclusion, both role-playing and simulation games are played "rarely" by the Grade Four pupils in the three schools of Valencia City District III. The overall mean response for role-playing games is 2.29, while for simulation games, it is slightly higher at 2.42.

Table 5. *The Frequency of Playing Sports and Strategy Games*

<i>Sports Games</i>		<i>Mean</i>	<i>Rank</i>	<i>Description</i>
1.	Soccer	2.62	1	Sometimes
2.	Golf	2.43	2	Rarely
3.	FIFA	2.29	3	Rarely
4.	Tony Walk	2.23	4	Rarely
5.	Maden	2.17	5	Rarely
Over All Mean		2.35		Rarely
<i>Strategy Games</i>		<i>Mean</i>	<i>Rank</i>	<i>Description</i>
1.	Chess Master	2.43	1	Rarely
2.	Red Alert	2.34	2	Rarely
3.	Star Craft	2.26	3.5	Rarely
4.	Roller Coaster Tycoon 3	2.26	3.5	Rarely
5.	Civilization IV	2.25	5	Rarely
Over All Mean		2.31		Rarely

Note: The scale use in the table is never (1.00-1.80), rarely (1.81 – 2.60), sometimes (2.61 – 3.40), most of the time (3.41 – 4.20), and always (4.21 – 5.00)

Table 5 presents the frequency of playing sports and strategy games. The sports games considered in this study include Madden, Fifa, Tony Hawk, Soccer, and Golf, while the strategy games include Roller Coaster Tycoon 3, Red Alert, Civilization IV, Starcraft, and Chessmaster. Among the sports games, Soccer had the highest mean response of 2.62, indicating that it is "sometimes" played by the pupils. In the strategy games category, Chessmaster ranked highest with a mean response of 2.43, indicating it is "rarely" played. The rest of the sports games, with mean responses ranging from 1.81 to 2.60, are also considered "rarely" played. Similarly, the other strategy games, such as Red Alert (2.34), Roller Coaster Tycoon 3 (2.26), Starcraft (2.26), and Civilization IV (2.25), are also "rarely" played, with only slight differences in mean responses among them.

The overall frequency of playing different types of video games among Grade Four pupils in the three schools of Valencia City District III is summarized in Table 6. It shows that, of all the game types, fighting games rank first as the most played, with a mean response of 4.13, rated as "most of the time." This finding aligns with Funk's (1993) research, which suggests that children tend to prefer video games with violent content, such as fighting games.

Simulation and puzzle games are ranked second, both with a mean response of 2.42, indicating that they are "rarely" played. Sports games rank third with a mean response of 2.35, also rated as "rarely" played. Strategy games follow, with a mean response of 2.31, indicating they are "rarely" played as well. Role-playing games are also "rarely" played, with a mean of 2.29. Action games are ranked next with a mean response of 2.25, also indicating they are "rarely" played. Finally, adventure games have the lowest mean response of 1.96, indicating that they are the least played by the pupils.

Table 6. *Summary table on the frequency of playing video games in terms of types*

<i>Video Games</i>		<i>Mean</i>	<i>Rank</i>	<i>Description</i>
1.	Action Games	2.25	7	Rarely
2.	Adventure Games	1.96	8	Rarely
3.	Fighting Games	4.13	1	Most of the time
4.	Puzzle Games	2.42	2.5	Rarely
5.	Role-Playing Games	2.29	6	Rarely
6.	Simulations Games	2.42	2.5	Rarely
7.	Sports Games	2.35	4	Rarely
8.	Strategy Games	2.31	5	Rarely
Overall		2.51		Sometimes

Note: The scale use in the table is never (1.00-1.80), rarely (1.81 – 2.60), sometimes (2.61 – 3.40), most of the time (3.41 – 4.20), and always (4.21 – 5.00)

In general, the most frequently played video game type by Grade Four pupils in the three schools of Valencia City District III is fighting games, while the other types of video games are rated as "rarely played." Adventure games are the least frequently played. This suggests that the Grade Four pupils in the three schools involved in the study have a preference for playing video games that contain violent content.

Problem 2. How much time do they spend on playing video games per week?

Monitoring the number of hours children played video games is significant because too much video gaming can interfere with a person's life, hurting things like school performance and friendships. The time spent in playing video games per week can be gleaned in Table 7.

Table 7. Time Spent Playing Video Games per Week

Video Games	1-3 Hrs	4-6 Hrs	7-9 Hrs	10+ Hrs
1. Action Games	64 (58.7%)	26 (23.9 %)	10 (9.2%)	9 (8.3%)
2. Adventure Games	48 (44.0%)	35 (32.1%)	20 (18.3%)	6 (5.5%)
3. Fighting Games	58 (53.2%)	31 (28.4%)	16 (14.7%)	4 (3.7%)
4. Puzzle Games	65 (59.6%)	25 (22.9%)	13 (11.9%)	6 (5.5%)
5. Role-playing Games	63 (57.8%)	33 (30.3%)	7 (6.4%)	6 (5.5%)
6. Simulation Games	72 (66.1%)	22 (20.2%)	9 (8.3%)	6 (5.5%)
7. Sports Games	63 (57.8%)	23 (21.1%)	16 (14.7%)	7 (6.4%)
8. Strategy Games	77 (70.6%)	19 (17.4%)	7 (6.4%)	6 (5.5%)
Total	58%	25%	11%	6%

Note. The percentage recorded in parentheses indicates the percentage of the time spent playing video games per week.

The results showed that among the 109 respondents in this study, 58% of pupils played video games for 1-3 hours per week, 25% played for 4-6 hours, 11% played for 7-9 hours, and only 6% played for more than 10 hours per week. This suggests that the majority of Grade Four pupils in the three schools of Valencia City District III spend relatively little time playing video games each week. Consequently, the effects of video games on these children, particularly in relation to their studies, are likely to be minimal. Furthermore, the Grade Four pupils in these schools do not appear to be addicted or obsessed with video games, despite the availability of numerous games in their community or barangay. The pupils engage in other activities more frequently than playing video games.

Problem 3. How do teachers perceive the effect of video games on work and study attitudes of Grade Four pupils?

The influence of video games on the work and study attitudes of pupils, as perceived by the teachers, is presented in Table 8. The table includes the mean responses from the teachers for each item, along with the corresponding rank and verbal description reflecting their level of agreement with the statements.

Table 8. Effect Of Video Games On Work And Study Attitudes Of Grade Four Pupils As Perceived By The Teachers

Indicators	Mean	Rank	Description
1. Children Spend More Time Playing Video Games Than Reading Their Books.	4.80	1.5	Strongly Agree
2. Children prefer to play violent/fighting games than educational games.	4.80	1.5	Strongly Agree
3. Playing video games affects the study habit of children.	4.40	3	Strongly Agree
4. Video games can cause frequent cutting of class.	4.20	4	Agree
5. Children who play video games are inattentive.	4.00	5.5	Agree
6. Children who play video games are playful.	4.00	5.5	Agree
7. Playing video games make the child lazy.	3.80	8.5	Agree
8. Video games child easily gets angry.	3.80	8.5	Agree
9. Children who play video games cannot easily follow directions.	3.80	8.5	Agree
10. Playing violent games lead to aggressive.	3.80	8.5	Agree
11. Children who play video games are always sleepy during class hours.	3.60	11	Agree
12. Video games can cause poor performance in academic subjects.	3.40	12.5	Undecided
13. Playing video games is considered as "time wasters"	3.40	12.5	Undecided
14. Children who play video games may engage in fights with their peers.	3.20	14.5	Undecided
15. Children who play video games are disrespectful.	3.20	14.5	Undecided
16. Children who play video games are prone to confrontation with teachers.	3.00	16	Undecided
17. Children who play video games do make more mistakes.	2.80	17	Undecided
18. Children who play video games are cheaters.	2.60	18	Disagree
19. Children cannot learn from video games	2.40	19	Disagree
20. Video games are not beneficial to children.	2.40	20	Disagree
Over All Mean	3.57		Agree

Note: The scale use in the table is strongly disagree (1.00-1.80), disagree (1.81 – 2.60), undecided (2.61 – 3.40), agree (3.41 – 4.20), and strongly agree (4.21 – 5.00).

The results indicate that teachers strongly agree that children spend more time playing video games than reading their books, with a mean response of 4.80, making it the highest-ranked item. This discovery corresponds with a report from the Archives of Paediatrics & Adolescent Medicine, Science Daily (July 2, 2007), indicating that, on school days, adolescent males who engage in video gaming typically allocate less time to reading, whereas adolescent females who partake in video gaming devote less time to homework compared to their non-gaming counterparts.

This finding, however, contradicts Skoric et al. (2009), who proposed that children who invest considerable time in gaming also dedicate ample time to schoolwork and sustain satisfactory grades.

The second-highest-ranked item, equal to the preceding statement, suggests that youngsters like violent or combat games over instructive ones. Teachers concur significantly (mean response of 4.40) that video game engagement influences children's study habits, positioning this item in the second rank. This corroborates the findings of the National Institute of Mental Health (2005), which indicated that excessive video game engagement might result in communication difficulties with family and friends and adversely

affect academic or professional life. Furthermore, it substantiates Anderson and Dill's (2000) assertion that increased duration of video game play may lead to diminished academic achievement.

The statement that video games can cause frequent class cutting (mean response of 4.20) is rated as "agree" and is ranked third. Teachers also agree that children who play video games tend to be inattentive and playful, which are tied for fourth rank. Other statements, such as video games making children lazy, easily angered, aggressive, and unable to follow directions, all tie for fifth rank with a mean response of 3.80. These results align with Anderson et al. (2010), who asserted that violent video games enhance aggressive cognition, emotions, physiological arousal (such as heart rate and blood pressure), and aggressive conduct.

Further, teachers agreed that children who play video games tend to be sleepy during class hours (mean response of 3.60), ranking sixth. This may indicate that children are so deeply involved in gaming that it affects their sleep patterns.

Nonetheless, certain assertions were contested by the teachers based on their observations. Teachers contested the assertion that video games lack benefits for children, endorsing the position of Virvou, Katsionis, and Manos (2005), who observed that certain teachers regard educational games as unhelpful. Teachers also contested the notion that children are incapable of learning from video games, corroborating the findings of the Kaiser Family Foundation (2003), which indicated that 72% of parents of young children assert that computer usage "mostly helps" children's learning, whereas merely 5% contend it "mostly hurts." Dunkin and Baeber (2002) observed that pupils who engage in computer gaming demonstrate a greater devotion to education. Teachers also contested the assertion that pupils who engage in video gaming are dishonest.

In overall view, the teachers in the three schools of Valencia City District III agreed that video games could affect the works and study attitudes of the Grade Four pupils with mean response of 3.57.

Problem 4. Is there a significant difference in the frequency of playing video games between male and female pupils?

Table 9 presents the results of the two-sample t-test on the frequency of playing video games. The means of the responses from the two groups, along with their corresponding standard deviations, are also shown. The two-sample t-test is a statistical method used to test for significant differences between the independent responses of two normally distributed groups, assuming that both groups have equal variances. The analysis considers eight different types of video games and examines whether there is a significant difference in the frequency of playing each type.

Table 9. Two-Sample Independent T-Test On The Frequency Of Playing Video Games When Classified According To Gender

Action Games	Mean	Std. Dev.	T-Value	P-Value	Interpretation
Male	2.13	1.03	-1.64	0.105	Not Significant
Female	2.45	0.91			
Adventure Games	Mean	Std. Dev.	T-Value	P-Value	Interpretation
Male	1.89	1.08	-0.93	0.357	Not Significant
Female	2.09	1.11			
Fighting Games	Mean	Std. Dev.	T-Value	P-Value	Interpretation
Male	4.08	0.87	-0.810	0.420	Not Significant
Female	4.21	0.73			
Puzzle Games	Mean	Std. Dev.	T-Value	P-Value	Interpretation
Male	2.29	1.04	-1.66	0.101	Not Significant
Female	2.64	1.11			
Role-Playing Games	Mean	Std. Dev.	T-Value	P-Value	Interpretation
Male	3.50	0.91	-11.42	0.000	Significant
Female	5.51	0.87			
Simulation Games	Mean	Std. Dev.	T-Value	P-Value	Interpretation
Male	2.41	1.08	-0.107	0.915	Not Significant
Female	2.43	0.90			
Sports Games	Mean	Std. Dev.	T-Value	P-Value	Interpretation
Male	2.39	1.21	0.442	0.659	Not Significant
Female	2.29	1.13			
Strategy Games	Mean	Std. Dev.	T-Value	P-Value	Interpretation
Male	2.32	1.17	0.182	0.856	Not Significant
Female	2.28	1.14			

Note: The table indicates the two-sample independent T-Test on the frequency of playing video games when classified according to gender. It indicates whether there is a significant difference in the frequency of playing video games between male and female pupils.

The results indicate that there is no significant difference in the frequency of playing action, adventure, fighting, puzzle, simulation, sports, and strategy games between male and female pupils in Valencia Elementary Schools. The computed t-values for these games are small, and their corresponding p-values exceed the level of significance (0.05), suggesting that gender does not influence the frequency of playing these video games.

However, the frequency of playing role-playing games shows a significant difference when classified by gender. The computed p-value is 0.00, which is less than the level of significance (0.05). Additionally, the computed t-value is -11.42, which is large, leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis.

This result indicates that gender influences the frequency of playing role-playing games. The mean responses reveal that female pupils (mean = 5.51) play role-playing games more frequently than male pupils (mean = 3.50), which is consistent with the negative sign of the computed t-value.

Conclusions

Based on the findings, several conclusions can be drawn. First, fighting games were the most preferred type of video game among the Grade Four pupils in the three schools of Valencia City District III. However, this preference raises concerns, as these games may not be suitable for the pupils. The content in such games could potentially influence behavior, leading pupils to replicate actions in real life or diminish their fear of making mistakes.

Second, although pupils spend relatively little time playing video games per week, this means they have more opportunities to engage in other beneficial activities, such as spending time with their families, reading books, completing homework, and studying their lessons.

Lastly, teachers believe that video games have a significant impact on the work and study attitudes of Grade Four pupils. Consequently, it is recommended that the time spent on video games be minimized, with a focus on moderation to reduce any negative effects on pupils' academic and personal development.

Based on the findings and conclusions of the study, the following recommendations are provided:

For parents, it is essential to monitor the types of games their children play and ensure they are age-appropriate. Parents may avoid purchasing games that contain excessive violence and instead opt for educational games that promote learning. Additionally, parents should offer children alternative forms of entertainment that support their overall physical and mental development.

For teachers, it is recommended that they closely monitor pupils who frequently miss class or cut class, conducting daily attendance checks both in the morning and afternoon. To keep pupils engaged and alert, teachers may use colorful and attractive visual aids during lessons. Teachers should also remind pupils not to visit computer shops during class hours and, if a pupil consistently cuts class, they should contact the parents to address the issue.

For pupils, it is advised that they choose educational games over violent ones, always obey their parents and teachers, and avoid going to computer shops during class hours to ensure they remain focused on their studies.

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